

HYPOCHLORITE OXIDATION OF STARCHES. PART II. RATE OF OXIDATION OF STARCHES

BY M. C. PATEL, B. N. MANKAD AND R. D. PATEL

VITHALBHAI PATEL MAHAVIDYALAYA, VALLABHVIDYANAGAR

(Received June 21, 1954)

Interaction of starch solution with sodium hypochlorite solutions under different conditions of H^+ - ion concentration has been studied.

Nabar and Vyas attempted to study the rate of oxidation of maize, rice, sagó and arrowroot starches with $NaOCl$ solution at different pH and determined the amount of oxygen uptake at different periods (vide Part I).

Moreover, in the case of maize starch they observed that the rate of oxidation decreased as the pH moved from 3 to 5. At about this pH , the rate of oxygen uptake was minimum and rose rapidly as the neutral point approached, reaching a maximum value at about pH 7.2. The rate then slowly decreased on the other side of neutrality.

In the present investigation the study of the rate of oxidation has been applied to a number of starches under varied conditions. The fundamental variation in the experimental procedure adopted in this work is that the interaction of the starch with the hypochlorite solution has been carried out by taking starch in aqueous solution.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Starch solutions (1%) were prepared by keeping a weighed quantity of starch with water in a boiling water-bath for 3 hours. In conical flasks (coloured black) 20 ml. of the solution was mixed with 30 ml. of buffer solution and the requisite volume of standard $NaOCl$ solution, and finally the volume was made up to 60 ml. The flasks were immediately kept in a thermostat having a controlled temperature of $35^\circ \pm 1^\circ$. Simultaneously blank experiments were carried out. At intervals of 15, 30, 60, 90, 120, 150 and 180 minutes 5 ml. was withdrawn and titrated against standard (0.045N) thiosulphate solution after adding 4 ml. of 10% KI solution and 10 ml. of 10% acetic acid. The quantity of oxygen consumed was calculated by difference.

Results obtained are shown graphically in Figs. 1, 2 and 3. From the results it appears that the oxygen uptake at the end of 3 hours for different starches is

FIG. 1
Cereals.

FIG. 2
Pulses.

FIG. 3
Tubers and roots.

$p_{H_2} = 6.95$, Conc. of NaOCl = 2g. av. Cl₂/litre (Figs. 1-3),

different. The order of oxygen uptake is found as : rice>wheat>kodri>bajri>cheno>maize>bavto, juvar in cereals ; vale>maga>chana>chola>tuver in pulses and kand>shakaria>shingodan in tubers and roots. In case of pulses the orders of oxygen uptake in solid state was quite in a reverse way. The general mode of oxygen uptake is similar in case of cereals, pulses, tubers and roots.

The disposition of the curves is almost identical in all varieties. However, the curves for maize and bajri show that after one hour the rate of oxidation suddenly decreases.

FIG. 4
Effect of pH on optimum O_2 uptake.

In order to determine the oxygen up take of starches at different pH , two representative samples of each variety of starch were selected from each group. The solution of each sample was treated with hypochlorite solution after adjusting the pH with buffers. The results obtained are recorded in Table I and Fig. 4.

TABLE I

Variety of starch.	pH				
	5.40.	6.39.	6.95.	8.2.	9.15.
	Oxygen uptake in mg.				
Maize	6.450	5.590	9.632	2.752	2.666
Bajri	8.514	7.482	10.234	1.462	...
Tuver	5.246	5.504	5.332	2.838	2.666
Chola	5.160	5.160	6.364	0.946	...
Shakaria	4.730	4.300	5.160	0.592	...
Shingodan	4.902	5.160	4.042	1.204	0.860

From the comparative study of the curves the following conclusions are reached.

The value of optimum oxygen uptake is highest at p_H 7. On either side of neutral point the value decreases. The tendency towards the decrease is more pronounced on the alkaline side than on the acidic side. In the case of maize and bajri, there is a tendency to have a greater oxygen uptake at lower p_H . The disposition of their curves is quite similar.

The maize and tuver starches do not show the analogy which has been observed during oxidation in a solid state.

If the nature of the curves is taken as a basis for a comparison of different varieties of starch, the clear resemblance is seen in the pairs : maize and bajri ; chola and shakaria ; tuver and shingodan.

The authors' thanks are due to Dr. M. D. Avasare and Dr. C. C. Shah for their keen interest in the work.